

Importance of defective structure of ceria additive on selectivity and stability of carbon-supported low-Pt-content-catalysts during oxygen reduction

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ABSTRACT

Benchmark carbon/Vulcan-supported Pt nanoparticles have been subjected to interfacial modification with defective ceria (CeO_x , $1.5 < x \leq 2$) nanostructures to clarify the influence of the metal oxide additive on the activity, selectivity, and stability of the low-Pt-content (Pt loading, $15 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$) electrocatalysts during the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) in acidic medium. The prepared three-component (Pt, C, CeO_x) hybrid catalytic materials have been rigorously characterized by X-ray diffraction, Raman spectroscopy, transmission electron microscopy, and near-ambient pressure X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (NAP-XPS), while the electrocatalytic and general electrochemical properties have been diagnosed using rotating ring-disk electrode (RRDE) voltammetry, chronocoulometry, and gas diffusion electrode methods. The NAP-XPS and Raman data have revealed that, among the distinct ceria additives studied, fine nanoparticles of cerium oxide deposited *in situ* on Vulcan XC-72 support are characterized by the most considerably defective structure with a noticeable amount of Ce(III). The results of electrochemical and NAP-XPS experiments imply the existence of strong mutual interactions between the defective ceria, platinum, and carbon components. The substoichiometric features of the ceria additive have been correlated with the ability of the low-Pt-content hybrid catalyst to minimize the formation of the undesirable hydrogen peroxide intermediate and promote the 4-electron ORR. On the whole, the addition of CeO_x/C to Vulcan-supported Pt catalyst leads to their improved durability during prolonged potential cycling under RRDE voltammetric conditions. In the presence of ceria, the desorptive oxidation of poisoning CO-type adsorbates (that may originate from corrosion of carbon carriers) is largely enhanced.

1. Introduction

The Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell (PEMFC) technology is one of the most promising solutions to generate electricity in response to the global rise of energy consumption associated with severe environmental issues, including possible climate changes [1–4]. The joint of high efficiency with low emitted pollution level gives them a great advantage over conventional power sources. However, the performance and operational cost of PEMFC largely depend on the application of highly expensive state-of-the-art Pt-based systems, which are so far the most effective catalysts for the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) at the fuel cell's cathode [2,5,6]. The widespread commercialization of the PEMFC technology has also been complicated by the limited lifetime of

catalytic systems due to the instability of carbon supports as well as Pt catalytic centers [7,8]. Despite intense efforts to develop noble-metal-free replacements, platinum nanostructures still seem to be an indispensable main component for ORR in acid media [9–11]. To keep down operational costs of PEMFCs, there is a need to minimize Pt loadings at the cathode while maintaining the overall high activity in ORR. Unfortunately, low-Pt-content catalytic systems often generate higher quantities of undesirable, highly corrosive hydrogen peroxide intermediate [12]. Consequently, it is of great significance to gain an in-depth insight into the ORR mechanism to optimize the activity of the ORR catalytic centers and their more efficient utilization while minimizing the Pt content without loss of performance and durability, which are essential features to ensure wider use of the low-temperature

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hydrogen-oxygen fuel cell systems [13,14].

Among reasonable strategies for improving the activity, selectivity, and stability of carbon-supported low-Pt-content electrocatalysts for the ORR in acid media is to consider their admixing or functionalization with certain nanostructured metal oxides [15,16]. At such hybrid catalytic interfaces utilizing certain metal oxides (e.g., CeO₂, WO₃, Ta₂O₅, Nb₂O₅, ZrO₂), Pt centers and nanostructured carbon carriers tend to be stabilized while the system exhibits high activity toward the four-electron (most efficient) reduction of oxygen. Among rare earth metal oxides with interlayer defects and oxygen vacancies, cerium oxide (CeO_x, 1.5 < x < 2) has been used as a support for metallic nanoparticles in many catalytic reactions. The catalytic activity of CeO_x results from its unique structure, the ability of shuttling between Ce^{III} and Ce^{IV} oxidation states without disruption of structure, in addition to oxygen vacancies with localized electrons left behind in Ce 4*f* states, thus leading to the formation of Ce^{III} species capable of stretching and weakening the O–O bond strength of the adsorbed O₂ and H₂O₂ molecules. Practical utility of rare earth oxides is usually improved by integrating them with a conductive matrix or carrier. Among a few rare earth metal oxides whose application is considered in ORR [17–19], the catalytic activity of CeO_x has received the most attention in the literature [20–23]. Indeed, the sub-stoichiometric cerium oxide (CeO_x) is known as the oxidative scavenger for free radicals, as well as the catalyst for hydrogen peroxide decomposition, which both are highly important in the context of the long-term durability of membrane electrode assemblies in fuel cells because of corrosive properties of these products [24–27]. A beneficial role of the defective structure of ceria has been emphasized in the context of strong interfacial Pt–CeO_x interactions, resulting in favorable tuning of Pt electronic structure and the stabilization of catalytic Pt sites [28–30]. In addition, the improved durability of the highly active triple-junction interface composed of Pt and CeO₂ nanostructures, as well as carbon carriers has been pointed out in the literature [31–33].

In the present work, having in mind an ultimate goal of minimizing the content of Pt while keeping the reasonably high catalytic system's activity, we address chemical identity and explore the unique properties of the CeO_x/C additive consisting of very fine nanoparticles of the reduced cerium oxide uniformly deposited on Vulcan XC-72 carbon support (prepared through a facile and one-step microwave-assisted hydrothermal method). Here the application of the sub-stoichiometric (defective) ceria as an additive for Vulcan-supported low Pt-content electrocatalyst has been verified during ORR in acid medium. The results are consistent with the view that the introduction of CeO_x tends to decrease the formation of the undesirable hydrogen peroxide intermediate and enhance the stability of the three-component system during long-term ORR experiments. On mechanistic grounds, while result of electroanalytical approaches permit us to comment on the systems' electrocatalytic performance, the near-ambient pressure XPS (NAP-XPS) experiments provide insight into the existence of mutual interactions between the defective ceria, platinum, and carbon components. The substoichiometric features of the ceria additive, which are evident from Raman spectroscopy, have been correlated with the ability of the low-Pt-content hybrid catalyst to minimize the formation of the undesirable hydrogen peroxide intermediate and promote the 4-electron ORR. In addition, we perform comparative diagnostic experiments with untreated and thermally pretreated ceria. Investigating and understanding the synergy between platinum, carbon, and cerium oxide seems to be of importance to the development of efficient electrocatalysts for ORR.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials

Cerium(III) nitrate hexahydrate (Ce(NO₃)₃·6 H₂O, 99 %), cerium(IV) oxide nanopowder (CeO₂, <25 nm particle size), and 5 wt% Nafion™ solution were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄, 95 wt%), ammonium solution (25 wt%), ethanol (EtOH, 99.8 %), and 2-

propanol (99.7 %) were purchased from Avantor Performance Materials Poland S.A. Model soot – Vulcan XC-72 was obtained from Cabot. The commercial platinum catalyst (20 wt% Pt/Vulcan XC-72; hereafter labeled as Pt/C) was purchased from the Fuel Cell Store. Oxygen, argon, and hydrogen-argon (1 % H₂) gases (99.999 % purity) were supplied by Air Products (Poland). All aqueous solutions were prepared using ultrapure deionized water obtained from a Millipore Milli-Q system with a resistivity of 18 MΩ cm. Measurements were performed at room temperature (22±2 °C).

2.2. Preparation and utilization of ceria additives

2.2.1. Hydrothermal synthesis of cerium oxide/carbon black

The reduced cerium oxide *in situ* deposited on carbon support was prepared by microwave-assisted hydrothermal route [34]. First, a known amount of the Vulcan XC-72 was dispersed in ethanol (0.01 g carbon per cm³ EtOH) and ultrasonicated for at least 30 min to achieve good dispersion. To the as-prepared carbon suspension, an appropriate amount of the 0.2 mol dm⁻³ solution of cerium nitrate and the stoichiometric amount of ammonia solution (25 wt%) were added at room temperature. The resultant mixture was then transferred to a Teflon-lined microwave autoclave (Ertec/MAGNUM II, Wrocław, Poland). The reaction temperature was kept at 150 °C for 20 min. The product was centrifuged and washed several times with distilled water and ethanol and then dried at a temperature of 80 °C overnight. Considering the amount of the used constituents during synthesis, the content of the carbon deposited cerium oxide was estimated as 20 wt%. Hereafter, the obtained final sample (cerium oxide dispersed on the Vulcan XC-72) will be labeled as CeO_x/C.

2.2.2. Reductive heat treatment of commercial cerium oxide

For the sake of comparison and gaining additional information, commercial cerium oxide samples were subjected to heat treatment in the reducing atmosphere. Briefly, known amounts of the commercial cerium(IV) oxide nanopowder and carbon matrix (Vulcan XC-72) were mixed in a mortar for around 15 min, followed by treatment in a tubular furnace at 600, 800, or 900 °C for 4 h (at a heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹) under an ArH₂ (1 % H₂) flow (100 mL min⁻¹). In this case, the content of the cerium oxide was estimated as mentioned before (20 wt%). The resulting samples are denoted as CeO₂+C_{HT}, where HT corresponds to the heating temperature, e.g., CeO₂+C₉₀₀.

2.3. Materials characterization

2.3.1. Physicochemical characterization

The as-prepared powder samples were characterized for their phase structure and crystallinity by X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) using a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer with Cu Kα radiation. Data were recorded in the angle (2θ) range of 5–90° with a step of 0.012°. The average crystal size was calculated with the Scherrer equation from the broadening of peaks of CeO₂. The Raman spectra were recorded at room temperature using a Thermo Scientific DXR Raman microscope, with a resolution of 2 cm⁻¹ and the 50x-magnification lens. The excitation wavelength of 532 nm was used and the laser power at the sample position was set as about 3 mW. At least eight scans for each measurement were accumulated to optimize the signal-to-noise ratio. TEM investigations were carried out on the FEI Talos F200X microscope operated at 200 kV. Observations were performed in scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) mode using high-angle annular dark field (HAADF) imaging. Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) using a Super-X system with four silicon drift detectors (SDDs) was applied to detect differences in local chemical composition. The near-ambient pressure X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (NAP-XPS) profiles were collected using an EnviroESCA instrumentation from Specs, which mounted an Al Kα excitation source (hν = 1486.6 eV). The measurements were carried out at a pressure of about 10⁻⁶ mbar. The survey scan

was determined at a pass energy of 100 eV; each step had a width of 1.0 eV and was collected in 0.2 seconds. High-resolution spectra were collected at a pass energy of 40 eV; each step had a width of 0.05 eV and was collected in 0.2 seconds. The binding energy (BE) values were characterized by an uncertainty of ± 0.2 eV. The correction for charging was obtained by attributing a BE value of 284.8 eV to the C 1s peak of adventitious hydrocarbon, in compliance with the literature [35]. The NAP-XPS profiles were fitted by means of the software "Keystone" provided by Specs; a Shirley-type background function was used [36]. The sensitivity factors for integrated peak areas used for quantification purposes were provided by Specs. The parameters were selected to maximize the signal-to-noise ratio, at the same time ensuring that the samples did not undergo degradation triggered by X-ray exposure during the measurements, as already mentioned in the literature [37].

2.3.2. Electrochemical measurements and diagnosis of ORR catalytic activity

General electrochemical characteristics and electrocatalytic activity of the ceria-modified Pt/C towards the ORR in an acidic medium were determined using CH Instruments (Austin, TX, USA) model 735E workstation and a rotating ring-disk electrode (RRDE) assembly (RRDE-3A ver. 2.0, ALS Co., Ltd, Japan). The catalytic ink was prepared by mixing 3.80 mg of the commercial Pt/C, 4.56 mg of the selected obtained cerium oxide, 40 μl of 5 wt% Nafion solution, 2.5 cm^3 of H_2O , and 2.5 cm^3 of 2-propanol. The ink was sonicated for 30 min to form a homogenous suspension. Then, an appropriate amount of the ink was dropped onto the surface of a glassy carbon disk electrode to achieve the Pt loading on the electrode of 15 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The electrochemical measurements were conducted in a standard three-electrode electrochemical cell equipped with a glassy carbon disk working electrode (GCE surface area = 0.1256 cm^2), concentrically surrounded by a platinum ring, an Au counter electrode, and a Hg/Hg₂SO₄ (K₂SO₄-saturated) reference electrode. Before modification, the working electrode was polished with successively finer grade aqueous alumina slurries (grain size, 1–0.05 μm) on a Buehler polishing cloth. The electrolyte was 0.5 mol dm^{-3} H_2SO_4 aqueous solution saturated with either O₂ or Ar by bubbling the corresponding gas prior to each experiment and, then, during the tests. In order to obtain an electrochemically clean and stable catalyst surface, a modified working electrode, prepared according to the procedure described above, was activated by performing several full voltammetric potential cycles in the potential range between 0.05 and 1 V vs. RHE (Reversible Hydrogen Electrode) in an Ar-saturated electrolyte (at 100 mV s^{-1}) until stable results were obtained (typically about 50 scans). The general electrochemical properties of the obtained materials were determined by cyclic voltammetry (CV) in a deoxygenated electrolyte at a scan rate of 20 mV s^{-1} . The ORR activity of the prepared materials was tested in an O₂-saturated 0.5 mol dm^{-3} H_2SO_4 solution using linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) at a scan rate of 20 mV s^{-1} on the disk electrode, while the constant potential of 1.2 V vs. RHE was applied to the ring electrode, with several rotating speeds ranging between 600 and 2000 rpm. The accelerated stress tests (AST) of catalysts were performed by cycling in a potential range of 0.6–1.2 V vs. RHE in a deoxygenated electrolyte. After 500 cycles, the ORR activity of tested materials was again evaluated. Chronocoulometric measurements [38] were performed in the double potential step mode, and the responses of charge versus square root of time (linear Anson plots) were considered to separate the electrode surface phenomena from the bulk electrochemical process. In the forward potential steps, the potentials were shifted from the initial potential of 1.0 V (at which the electrocatalytic system was preconditioned for 20 s) to the final potential of 0.3 V (which was sufficiently negative to drive ORR). The cathodic forward potential steps were immediately followed by the reverse anodic backward potential steps. Intercepts with a charge axis (i.e., charges devoted to those interfacial processes) reflect not only double layer-charging but also surface electrochemistry of the catalytic layer (e.g., oxidation and reduction of carbon carriers).

All potentials reported here were recalculated and expressed vs. Reversible Hydrogen Electrode (RHE) ($E_{\text{Hg}/\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4} = 0.680$ V vs. RHE in 0.5 mol dm^{-3} H_2SO_4), the registered currents were normalized to the geometric area of the electrode and additionally corrected for the background currents. The onset (E_{onset}) and the half-wave ($E_{1/2}$) potentials values were determined as the potentials at the current density corresponded to 5 % and 50 % of the diffusion-limited current density, respectively [39].

The performance of examined catalysts was also tested at 60 ± 2 °C with a gas diffusion electrode (GDE, geometric area of active part, 3 cm^2) mounted into a Teflon flex cell (Gaskatel GmbH, Kassel, Germany). A spiral PtIr wire and hydrogen reference electrode (the latter placed in an external salt bridge) served as counter and reference electrodes, respectively. The gas diffusion backing layer for electrocatalysts was a carbon cloth with a microporous layer (W1S1005, Fuel Cell Store, College Station, TX, U.S.A.). Catalytic layers were sprayed from the inks, in which the ratio of catalyst to Nafion® was the same as in the course of RRDE thin film studies. Here, the final loading of Pt was 50 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The current densities were normalized to the exact mass of platinum (determined by weighing the carbon cloth before and after the preparation of layers).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Physicochemical characterization

Some attention was paid to the physicochemical identity of ceria obtained by the microwave-assisted hydrothermal method. The XRD results, shown in Fig. S1, confirmed that the obtained ceria nanoparticles crystallized in the pure cubic phase (fluorite structure, *Fd3m*) [40,41]. Compared to the reference ceria sample, a noticeable broadening of the diffraction peaks was observed for CeO_x/C, suggesting that smaller particles were gained. The Scherrer average size of the hydrothermally obtained ceria nanoparticles was estimated to be around 3 nm, while the crystallite size of the reference oxide was ~25 nm. Furthermore, due to the use of the carbon support, a wide peak at ~23°, which was related to the graphite plane (002) and partially overlaps with the (111) peak of CeO₂, can also be distinguished [34,42].

Further analysis was performed by Raman spectroscopy, which is sensitive to local structure and the possibility of the formation of defects. In the case of a commercial CeO₂ sample in a predominantly oxidized form, only one main band is observed around 464 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to the triply degenerate F_{2g} vibrational mode (Fig. 1A) [43]. It is related to the oxygen stretching around Ce atoms in the tetrahedral sites of the fluorite structure [40,44]. On the Raman spectra of the hydrothermally synthesized ceria nanoparticles and the heat-treated ceria samples, the broadening and shifting to a lower frequency (~460 cm^{-1}) of this characteristic band are visible (Fig. 1B). This phenomenon is associated with the smaller crystallite size of the obtained cerium oxide, as well as with the possible partial reduction of Ce⁴⁺, leading to structural defects formation [43]. The generation of oxygen vacancies in the ceria structure implies the creation of twofold Ce³⁺ ions, which causes the lattice expansion and the clear red shift of the F_{2g} mode [45]. Moreover, the spectra of CeO_x/C also show a wide band at ~550–600 cm^{-1} , which confirmed the partial removal of oxygen to maintain the electric neutrality due to the substitution of Ce⁴⁺ ions by Ce³⁺ ions [46,47]. It was established that such oxygen vacancies tended to enhance the diffusion rate of the O²⁻ anion in the lattice, thereby increasing the ease with which the material was able to uptake and release oxygen which could be crucial for catalysis [48,49]. In addition, the low-intensity band at around ~250 cm^{-1} , characteristic of small ceria nanoparticles, was recorded and assigned to the O–Ce longitudinal stretching of atoms in the outermost layers [50]. In the case of the heat-treated ceria samples, the red shift of the F_{2g} band confirmed the generation of oxygen vacancies, however, additional bands are not clearly visible which can be related to different morphology and particle

Fig. 1. (A) Raman spectra of the heat-treated CeO_2+C and the hydrothermally synthesized CeO_x/C samples in comparison to the commercial non-modified ceria, with (B) showing the red shift of F_{2g} mode.

size, compared to CeO_x/C . Furthermore, with increasing temperature of heat treatment, the F_{2g} is shifted to a lower wavenumber, suggesting enhancing the formation of structural defects.

Transmission electron microscopy analysis confirmed the nanometric size of the prepared ceria samples. In the case of the hydrothermally synthesized CeO_x *in situ* deposited on the carbon support, the HAADF-STEM image (Fig. 2a₁) shows fine nanoparticles of cerium oxide (< 10 nm), which is in good agreement with XRD results. The EDX maps (Fig. 2a₂–a₄) indicate the uniform distribution of cerium and oxygen on the carbon matrix. The CeO_2+C 900 sample, consisting of commercial cerium oxide, is characterized by a bigger particle size in the range of around 25–40 nm (Fig. 2b₁). In addition, in this case, some aggregates of the oxide phase appeared, and its worse dispersion on the carbon support is pronounced (Fig. 2b₂–b₄). The differences between the dispersion and particle size of these samples influence the mutual contact between the oxide phase and Pt nanoparticles (Fig. S2A). Due to the better distribution of cerium oxide *in situ* deposited on carbon, a larger amount of oxide additive is in direct contact with the Pt active phase, which can imply stronger interactions between them, thereby affecting electrocatalytic activity. Moreover, similar sizes of nanoparticles may

determine the improved contact on the Pt and CeO_x interface. The presence of individual nano-components, including ceria, carbon, and platinum nanostructures is evident upon examination of representative high-resolution transmission electron microscopic (HRTEM) images (Fig. S2B). It is reasonable to assign lighter portions in the upper image to ceria overlayers (10–15 nm) on darker carbon carriers (30–40 nm), whereas dark dots in the lower image to the dispersed Pt nanoparticles being in contact with ceria and carbon nanostructures.

To investigate the surface composition and mutual interactions between all catalytic components, NAP-XPS spectra were recorded (Figs. 3 and 4; Fig. S3). The NAP-XPS data for commercial CeO_2 and its mixture with Vulcan XC-72 were also shown for comparison and to facilitate analysis. The surface exposure of cerium, as quantified by the atomic percent (at%) of cerium atoms detected on the exterior of the sample by NAP-XPS, was very different for the three additives considered in this work, decreasing significantly in the following order (Table 1): CeO_2 (3.9 at%) > CeO_x/C (0.9 at%) > CeO_2+C (0.11 at%). Further thermal treatment in a reducing environment has a minor effect on the surface exposure of Ce species on $\text{CeO}_2+\text{C}_{HT}$ ($HT = 600^\circ\text{C}$, 800°C , and 900°C).

In pristine CeO_2 , ca. 33.4 at% of Ce are Ce(III). In hydrothermally

Fig. 2. Microscopic TEM analysis of the (a) CeO_x/C and (b) $\text{CeO}_2+\text{C}_{900}$. The first column, (a₁–b₁), presents HAADF STEM images of the samples, whereas EDX results are presented in the a₂–b₄ columns.

Fig. 3. Decomposition of the C 1s profiles determined by NAP-XPS of the CeO₂-based additives and of the C reference.

Fig. 4. (a) Decomposition of the Pt 4f profiles determined by NAP-XPS of the nanocomposite systems and of the reference Pt/C. (b) Pt(0)/Pt(Ox) molar ratio of the nanocomposite systems and the reference Pt/C, as determined from the data displayed in (a). (c) Mole fraction of Ce(III) on the surface of the additives and of the nanocomposite systems.

obtained CeO_x/C, 43.5 at% of Ce are Ce(III). As CeO₂ is grown on C support, the latter provides a reducing environment favoring the occurrence of the lower oxidation state of Ce, *i.e.*, Ce(III). Finally, in CeO₂+C and CeO₂+C_{HT} ca. 21–24 at% of Ce are Ce(III) (Table 1). In this case, mixing of C with CeO₂ would lead to preferred interactions between C and Ce(III); hence, the latter would be more easily covered by C, resulting in a preferred exposure of Ce(IV). On these bases, we

Table 1

Main features of Ce species on the surface of additives as determined by NAP-XPS.

Additive	Overall at% of Ce on the surface	Molar Fraction of Ce(III) on the surface / %	Molar Fraction of Ce(IV) on the surface / %
CeO ₂	3.89	33.4	66.6
CeO _x /C	0.90	43.5	56.5
CeO ₂ +C	0.11	22.4	77.6
CeO ₂ +C ₆₀₀	0.1	21.5	78.5
CeO ₂ +C ₈₀₀	0.06	21.9	78.1
CeO ₂ +C ₉₀₀	0.12	23.6	76.4

conclude that the chemical state of cerium is affected by the different interactions with C in the various CeO₂-based additives. The decomposition of C 1s profiles of CeO₂-based additives and the C reference (Fig. 3) reveals that in the former group of samples, the introduction of Ce leads to an increased intensity of the components centered at ca. 285.3 eV and 289.0 eV, assigned respectively to sp³ C and COOH. This is ascribed to the establishment of direct interactions between CeO_x and C, stabilizing the above-mentioned oxidized C species.

Upon mixing reference Pt/C with the different CeO₂-based additives, a variety of new interactions are established between the various components of the final nanocomposite systems. Such interplays would include (i) direct interactions between the different species (*e.g.*, Pt-Ce and C-Ce); and (ii) spillover electronic interactions between Pt and Ce mediated by the C species present in the system.

The effect of these new interactions is detected clearly in the Pt 4f NAP-XPS profiles of the investigated nanocomposite systems (Fig. 4a). With respect to the reference Pt/C, in the nanocomposite systems both Pt 4f doublets, which are ascribed to Pt(0) and Pt(Ox) species, are shifted by ca. 0.3–0.5 eV to lower binding energies. In addition, in all the nanocomposite systems the Pt(0)/Pt(Ox) molar ratio is similar and much higher than in the reference Pt/C (~3.5:1 vs. 0.75:1, see Fig. 4b). On these bases, it is concluded that in the nanocomposite systems, the surface of Pt species is more reduced and richer in electrons. Correspondingly, upon mixing Pt/C with a CeO₂-based additive, the relative abundance of Ce(III) species in the resulting nanocomposite system is decreased (Fig. 4c). This is consistent with the establishment of an electron transfer from CeO₂ to Pt species in the final nanocomposite systems. In the case of Pt/C + CeO₂+C₉₀₀, the oxidation of Ce(III) is not readily observed due to the difficulty in quantifying the Ce(III)/Ce(IV) components associated with negligible surface exposure of Ce (less than 0.05 at%, also see Fig. S3 in Supplementary Information).

3.2. Electrocatalytic activity

The electrocatalytic activity of the obtained reduced ceria-modified Pt/C catalyst in the ORR was evaluated by RRDE voltammetric measurements in an O₂-saturated 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ aqueous solution at room temperature. As a reference, a commercial platinum catalyst (20 wt%Pt/Vulcan XC-72) was used. Due to the similarity of current-potential profiles for all tested samples (Fig. S4), in the main text, we show curves for the CeO_x/C-modified Pt/C to characterize the system (Fig. 5). The recorded voltammetric curves (Fig. 5B and S4B) for the tested samples exhibited the well-defined convective-diffusion-limited current densities in the range of 4.8–5 mA cm⁻² (or, when expressed against the loading/mass of Pt catalyst, 0.32–0.33 mA μg_{Pt}⁻¹ cm⁻²), in addition to the kinetic control region at the potential above 0.85 V vs. RHE. It is noteworthy that a loading of the Pt catalyst (15 μg cm⁻²) at the disk was always the same. Although this Pt-content was low but, on other hand, high enough to make the platinum activity a determinantal factor with respect to the observed limiting currents. A minor increase in the limiting current density, observed in the case of the catalyst with ceria additive could reflect changes in the mass transport through the porous catalytic layer due to the higher carbon content and the presence

Fig. 5. (A) CV curves for the CeO_x/C-modified Pt/C sample compared to the Pt/C benchmark in Ar-saturated 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ solution at the scan rate of 20 mV s⁻¹. LSV curves for the ORR on the CeO_x/C-modified Pt/C sample compared to the Pt/C benchmark in O₂-saturated 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ solution, (B) disk, and (C) ring currents. Ring potential 1.2 V vs. RHE, electrode rotation speed = 1600 rpm, disk potential scan rate = 20 mV s⁻¹. (D) Percent of H₂O₂ calculated from the RRDE measurements.

of metal oxide material. The activity of the obtained electrocatalysts was also assessed by determining the reduction potential in terms of the onset and half-wave potentials, which are summarized in Table 2. The highest reduction potential ($E_{\text{onset}} = 0.923$ V vs. RHE and $E_{1/2} = 0.807$ V vs. RHE) was found for the electrocatalyst containing the prepared CeO_x/C additive, showing the absence of any loss of performance in comparison to the reference Pt/C sample ($E_{\text{onset}} = 0.923$ V vs. RHE and $E_{1/2} = 0.804$ V vs. RHE). For the majority of the remaining tested catalysts, similar values were obtained in the range of $E_{\text{onset}} = 0.920$ – 0.922 V vs. RHE and $E_{1/2} = 0.800$ – 0.804 V vs. RHE. Only for the Pt/C + CeO₂+C₆₀₀ sample, a slight decrease in the onset potential was observed (0.917 V vs. RHE), which may originate from the limitations in the electrical conductivity of the least defective cerium oxide additive. The poorer dispersion of the heat-treated ceria samples and, consequently, inferior contact with the platinum active phase may also influence the electrocatalysts' activity.

In addition, the Tafel plots, presented in Fig. S5, were used to elucidate the ORR kinetics. The Tafel slopes were calculated for all the investigated catalysts, taking into account the mass transport correction for the calculation of the kinetic current density[51]:

Table 2
Electrocatalytic properties of the ceria-modified Pt/C, compared with the commercial Pt/C.

Sample	E_{onset} vs RHE/V @5 % j_{max}	$E_{1/2}$ vs RHE/V @50 % j_{max}	H ₂ O ₂ /%	
			@0.5 V	@0.6 V
Pt/C	0.923	0.804	1.67	0.98
Pt/C + CeO _x /C	0.923	0.807	1.12	0.73
Pt/C + CeO ₂ +C ₆₀₀	0.917	0.803	1.36	0.92
Pt/C + CeO ₂ +C ₈₀₀	0.920	0.804	1.32	0.84
Pt/C + CeO ₂ +C ₉₀₀	0.922	0.800	1.20	0.81

$$j_k = \frac{j_L \times j}{j_L - j} \quad (1)$$

where j_k is the mass transport corrected kinetic current density, j is the measured current density, and j_L is the convective-diffusion-limited current density. The common behavior for the Pt electrocatalysts was observed, with changing the Tafel slopes from ~ 65 mV dec⁻¹ in the low overpotentials region to ~ 120 mV dec⁻¹ in the high overpotentials region[52,53]. The obtained results slightly varied between the individual samples, implying the presence of the same type of active sites capable of activating oxygen molecules. The Pt mass-specific activity was determined at 0.9 V vs. RHE via normalization of the calculated j_k to the Pt-loading of the disk electrode (Table S1). The results showed some increase in the following order: Pt/C + CeO₂+C₆₀₀ < Pt/C + CeO₂+C₈₀₀ < Pt/C + CeO₂+C₉₀₀ ≤ Pt/C < Pt/C + CeO_x/C but it should be remembered that the differences were not significant.

To get better insight into the ORR mechanism and its electrocatalytic efficiency, there is a need to comment on the effective number of electrons involved in the process (the 4-electron reduction to H₂O vs. the 2-electron reduction to H₂O₂) and on the relative formation of the undesirable hydrogen peroxide intermediate. To delineate the pathways of ORR at the catalysts considered, such parameters as the number of the transferred electrons and the percent of the produced H₂O₂ species (with respect to the total ORR products) were determined from the recorded RRDE profiles using Eqs. (2) and (3), respectively [54]:

$$n = \frac{4 \times i_d}{i_d + \frac{i_r}{N}} \quad (2)$$

$$\%H_2O_2 = \frac{200 \times \frac{i_r}{N}}{i_d + \frac{i_r}{N}} \quad (3)$$

where i_d is the current measured at the GC disk, i_r is the current measured at the Pt ring, and N is the collection efficiency ($N = 0.424$).

Fig. 5D illustrates the percent content of H_2O_2 (based on the monitoring of the oxidation currents at the ring electrode) as a function of the potential applied to the disk electrode for the Pt/C + CeO_x/C sample, in comparison to Pt/C. For all studied catalysts, the formation of hydrogen peroxide begins at the potential ~ 0.85 V, then it rises at lower potentials (more sharply below 0.5 V) until reaching the maximum value at the region of the hydrogen underpotential deposition (on Pt). In the case of all the ceria-modified Pt/C electrocatalysts (Fig. S4D), a decreasing amount of the H_2O_2 -formation has been noticed in comparison to the reference sample of ceria-free Pt/C. Historically, this phenomenon was attributed to the ability of cerium oxide to decompose hydrogen peroxide and scavenge for free radicals, as reported in the literature earlier [24,25,55]. Indeed, the average percent of the formed H_2O_2 (in the range of 0.3–0.75 V) for the ceria-modified Pt/C varies from 1.50 % to 1.28 %. Consequently, the number of transferred electrons for tested samples was found to be around 3.95–3.97, thus implying a predominantly 4-electron pathway mechanism of oxygen reduction. Another important observation coming from Fig. 5D is that the percent amount of hydrogen peroxide is always lower at the ceria-modified Pt/C, relative to conventional Pt/C, and the difference is even more pronounced at potentials lower than 0.6 V (e.g., see values at 0.5 V in Table 2). Under such conditions, the substoichiometric and mixed-valent CeO_x is likely to act as cocatalyst supporting Pt toward decomposition of undesirable H_2O_2 .

In addition, the amount of the H_2O_2 formation at 0.6 V (vs. RHE) has been correlated with the degree of structural defects, defined in terms of the position F_{2g} Raman band characteristic of cerium oxide (Fig. 6). The use of CeO_x/C additive with the most considerable defective structure entails obtaining the smallest amount of produced H_2O_2 . In the case of remaining heat-treated ceria additives, generally, the higher temperature of reductive treatment enhances the formation of structural defects, thereby, the lower amount of the H_2O_2 -formed was noticed. It is reasonable to expect that a large population of oxygen vacancies and the existence of Ce^{III} -ionic sites (see the NAP-XPS section) in CeO_x/C additives improve morphological, adsorptive (activating), and redox conditions for the hydrogen peroxide decomposition (most likely reductive). It should be remembered, however, that ceria does not operate alone but together with platinum center and carbon carrier. It is apparent from our parallel diagnostic experiments that simple chemical decomposition of hydrogen peroxide induced by ceria alone is too slow to be effective during ORR. However, it was postulated that the inclusion of conductive materials, such as carbon, at the boundary with the metal oxide (CeO_x) was necessary to boost its catalytic activity [56]. Strong interactions between ceria and Pt, and the resulting surface electronic changes on platinum have been apparent from our NAP-XPS data. The coexistence of three components (Pt, CeO_x , C) at the electrocatalytic interface may be crucial when it comes to the decomposition of the hydrogen peroxide

Fig. 6. Correlation between the amount of H_2O_2 formation (at $E = 0.6$ V) on the ceria-modified Pt/C and the degree of structural defects of cerium oxide, defined based on the position F_{2g} Raman band.

intermediate, which is especially valuable in real PEM fuel cells.

The fact that RDE voltammetric responses recorded in the deoxygenated H_2O_2 -containing $0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$ at ceria-free and ceria-containing Pt/C electrodes do not significantly differ (Fig. S6) may reflect the high activity of platinum itself (even at low Pt-loading) toward H_2O_2 -reduction. When it comes to ORR, we believe that lowering the H_2O_2 production is a consequence of the strong electronic interaction between the substoichiometric ceria additive and the Pt catalytic active phase facilitating the direct 4-electron oxygen reduction mechanism, which translates to the increase of the overall number of transferred electrons (Fig. 7) and better electrocatalytic effectiveness.

The small size of ceria nanoparticles, comparable to that of platinum, together with good dispersion on the carbon support, make the obtained CeO_x/C a suitable additive for the low-Pt-content electrocatalysts. Based on microscopic studies, three components (Pt, C, CeO_x) are in close vicinity, and good contact between ceria and Pt as well as strong electronic interactions exist. Under such conditions, some improvement in the electrocatalysts' stability can be envisioned. To confirm this hypothesis, the AST (accelerated stability test) type diagnostic experiments have been performed (Fig. 8). First, some attention has been paid to changes in the characteristics of platinum by examining voltammetric background responses recorded in the deoxygenated electrolyte before and after subjecting the sample to 500 potential cycles at 100 mV s^{-1} from 0.6 to 1.2 V. It is apparent upon comparison of Curves a₁ and b₁ (Fig. 8), the decrease of the Pt-characteristic peaks (in the hydrogen adsorption range from 0 to 0.3 V; and for the oxidation of Pt to PtO at potentials at above 0.6 V) is much less pronounced in a case of ceria-containing system. In other words, decomposition or deactivation of platinum center seems to be much less pronounced in the presence of CeO_x . Careful examination of the cyclic voltammetric data (500-cycle diagnostic experiment) clearly implies that the most pronounced decrease of the Pt characteristic peaks occur following first 50 potential cycles (Fig. S7); further potential cycling of the CeO_x -modified system results in the relatively lower current decreases. The fact, that the addition of reduced ceria improves the stability of Pt/C electrocatalyst, can also be supported by the minor differences between oxygen reduction potential after subjecting the sample to 500 potential cycles (Fig. 8b₂).

In the case of the CeO_x -modified Pt/C, the E_{onset} and $E_{1/2}$ parameters have been shifted negatively about 21 mV and 22 mV, respectively (Fig. 8). In addition, a very low increase in the produced H_2O_2 was observed. For Pt/C reference samples, the higher differences between the determined reduction potentials are observable, in particular in the case of half-wave reduction potential ($\Delta E_{\text{onset}} = 22 \text{ mV}$, $\Delta E_{1/2} = 46 \text{ mV}$). The data are consistent with the enhancement of stability of the low-Pt-content CeO_x -containing hybrid electrocatalytic system.

The above stability tests were carried out in argon-saturated solutions. Under real condition, the catalyst would be operating in the oxygen-saturated solution. Fig. S8 illustrates cyclic voltammetric

Fig. 7. The number of transferred electrons during ORR, calculated from the RRDE measurements.

Fig. 8. Electrochemical characterization for as-received (solid lines) and after-durability-test (dashed lines) electrocatalysts: (a₁-a₃) Pt/C, and (b₁-b₃) Pt/C+CeO_x/C. (a₁,b₁) CV curves for the ceria-modified Pt/C sample compared to the Pt/C benchmark in Ar-saturated 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ solution at the scan rate of 20 mV s⁻¹. (a₂, b₂) LSV curves for the ORR on the ceria-modified Pt/C sample compared to the Pt/C benchmark in O₂-saturated 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ solution recorded at 1600 rpm and a scan rate of 20 mV s⁻¹. (a₃,b₃) Percentage of H₂O₂ calculated from the RRDE measurements.

responses recorded in deoxygenated solutions following application of 500 potential cycles (as for Fig. 8) in (a) argon-saturated and (b) oxygen-saturated H₂SO₄ electrolytes using the ceria-modified Pt/C. It is apparent upon comparison of curves a and b that the characteristic hydrogen adsorption peaks were only slightly lower when the 500-potential-cycling test was performed in the presence, rather than absence, of oxygen. Apparently, the addition of CeO_x exhibits the stabilization effect even under both electrochemically and chemically oxidative conditions.

In the stability context, another important issue seems to be the ability of CeO_x to interact strongly with the carbon matrix to undergo anchoring on carbon surfaces (see NAP-XPS section). To determine the interactions between carbon and ceria additive the chronocoulometry experiments were carried out. A very informative mode of recording the electrochemical data is to integrate the current and to report the charge passed as a function of time during the potential step experiment [38, 57]. In particular, the chronocoulometric response of charge (Q) versus square root of time (t^{1/2}) offers the possibility of separating the electrode surface phenomena (double layer-charging or surface electrochemistry of the catalytic layer) from the bulk electrochemical process (ORR). Figure S9 illustrates the results for the double-potential-step chronocoulometric experiments performed in the presence of oxygen at Pt/C in (A) the absence and (B) in the presence of the ceria additive. In the forward potential steps, the potentials have been shifted from the initial potential of 1.0 V (at which the electrocatalytic system has been preconditioned for 20 s) to the final potential of 0.3 V (which is sufficiently negative to enforce ORR). These cathodic forward potential steps have been immediately followed by the reverse anodic backward potential steps. While the cathodic portions of the plots of the diffusional-type charge originating from ORR are linear (Figs S9A and S9B), it is noteworthy that the respective Q vs. t^{1/2} responses have not passed through the origin because additional contributions to Q arising from double-layer charging as well as from electroreduction of any surface species (e.g. PtO, oxygen-containing groups on Vulcan) including molecules (e.g. CO₂) that might be generated and adsorbed at the time of

application of the starting (preconditioning) potential of 1.0 V. The charges devoted to those interfacial processes are passed very quickly when compared to the slow accumulation (potential pulse time, 5 s) of the diffusional component. Thus, two time-independent terms referring to surface processes appear (in addition to the diffusional part) in the integrated Cottrell equation:

$$Q = 2n_{\text{eff}}FA\pi^{-1/2}[D^{1/2}C_0] / t^{1/2} + Q_{\text{dl}} + nFA\Gamma_0 \quad (4)$$

where Q_{dl} is the capacitive charge, nFAΓ₀ quantifies the faradaic component characteristic of the catalyst's surface electrochemistry (A – geometric surface area, n – number of electrons involved in the surface process, F – Faraday constant), and Γ₀ stands for concentration (in mol cm⁻²), of the surface electroactive species. Obviously, as it was demonstrated before [57] examination of the slope, 2n_{eff}FAπ^{-1/2}[D^{1/2}C₀], permits to comment in absolute terms on the number of electrons effectively involved (n_{eff}) in ORR, provided that diffusion coefficient (D) and bulk concentration (C₀) of oxygen are known. Here we concentrate on the intercept values of Q vs. t^{1/2} which are equal to Q_{dl} + nFAΓ₀. Thus chronocoulometry permits us to comment on the surface phenomena occurring at the electrocatalytic interface. A simple examination of the approximate values of intercepts (nFAΓ₀ + Q_{dl}) in the Q-t^{1/2} implies that a value of the negative intercept is relatively larger than the positive one in the case of ceria-free Pt/C (Fig. S9A), whereas the respective intercepts are comparable for the ceria-containing Pt/C (Fig. S9B). It should be remembered that both electrocatalytic systems have been preconditioned for 20 s at the positive potential (1.0 V). Under such conditions, the surfaces of carbon nanostructures are oxidized to carbon oxo-species, in addition to the formation of PtO, and electrochemical charging of ceria additive. These features would certainly affect the values of the observed intercepts and it is not surprising that the interfacial charges are more sizeable in the presence of ceria. However, our general observation is that in the absence of ceria (Fig. S9A), the cathodic intercepts are larger than the respective anodic ones, whereas those intercepts are approximately equal in the system containing the ceria additive (Fig. S9B). This asymmetry in intercepts

may imply that the carbon oxo species, which are generated at 1.0 V (e.g., on the surfaces of Vulcan supports) in the absence of ceria, are not completely recovered (in the backward potential step) following their reduction (in the forward potential step). The observation reflects some irreversible processes most likely involving nanostructured carbon supports that eventually may lead to their degradation (e.g., through irreversible oxidation to CO_2). It seems that the asymmetry mentioned above has been much less pronounced upon the addition of ceria due to strong interactions between carbon carriers (in addition to platinum centers) with metal oxides, as postulated in earlier literature [15,58]. The feasibility of anchoring ceria on carbon surfaces has also been evident from our NAP-XPS data. This feature is expected to affect the carbon surface redox processes. In other words, the ceria-additive-containing system is fairly well-behaved with no degradation on the time scale of the experiment. A more detailed study of the surface processes occurring at the electrocatalytic interface during the reduction of oxygen will be the subject of our next communication.

As mentioned, during the long-term operation of fuel cells, corrosion of carbon carriers may result in the formation of CO_2 capable of adsorbing on Pt nanoparticles and poisoning their catalytic surfaces. In this respect, certain metal oxide additives were found to interact with Pt catalytic sites and to induce oxidative desorption of the poisoning/passivating CO adsorbates [15,58–60]. Our NAP-XPS data are also consistent with the existence of specific ceria-platinum interactions. An additional diagnostic voltammetric experiment has been performed to comment on the influence of the ceria additive on the oxidation of CO-adsorbates formed following the exposure of the catalytic system to CO_2 , subsequent interfacial reduction to CO and, finally its reoxidation (CO-stripping step).

Fig. 9 illustrates two background-subtracted CO-stripping-type voltammograms recorded at Vulcan-supported Pt in the presence (a) and in the absence (b) of ceria. A simple comparison of curves (a) and (b) implies that much larger CO-oxidation currents are observed at potentials higher than 0.5 V in the case of the system containing ceria additive. The explanation could be as follows: although CO_2/CO may be effectively adsorbed not only on Pt but also on ceria surfaces, the appearance of larger CO-oxidation currents (compare curves a and b) must reflect the higher ability of ceria-admixed Pt centers to oxidatively remove CO-poisoning adsorbates. This feature is expected to suppress the deactivation of Pt catalytic centers and may improve the durability of the catalyst's operation which is of importance during practical operation of the catalyst. Historically, it was reported in catalytic literature [61] that CO molecules could be efficiently oxidized over Pt/ceria catalysts. However, there was still some dispute about the stability and reactivity of different states of Pt. Also, a catalytic role of ceria-supported PtO_x sites with respect to enabling CO oxidation below room temperature was postulated.

Fig. 9. Background-current subtracted stripping-type voltammograms recorded for the oxidation of CO resulting from the spontaneous adsorption of CO_2 at 0.9 V for 20 s on the catalytic surfaces: (a) Pt/C with ceria additive; and (b) ceria-free Pt/C. Background currents were recorded in the deoxygenated 0.5 mol dm^{-3} electrolyte. Scan rate, 10 mV s^{-1} .

The performance of Pt/C+ CeO_x/C has also been tested by galvanodynamic measurements with the use of a gas diffusion electrode (GDE), mimicking the conditions existing in the low-temperature fuel cell. This specific type of cell allows for bypassing several drawbacks of the RRDE set-up resulting in experimental conditions far from a real device. One of the most important advantages, compared to the RRDE configuration, is the direct supply of gaseous oxygen to the cathode in the GDE cell, thus avoiding losses due to oxygen diffusion through the liquid electrolyte [62–64]. Due to the possibility of operating at fairly high current densities or even more elevated temperatures, we can assess the intrinsic catalytic activity of a chosen catalyst in three-electrode cells in the potential region relevant for operation in a PEMFC cathode. Because the catalyst loading varied slightly between the subsequent measurements, the obtained current data were normalized to the exact mass of platinum. Fig. 10 shows the resulting mass-specific ORR polarization curves of the Pt/C+ CeO_x/C and unmodified Pt/C catalysts in the GDE half-cell at 60°C . The results are consistent with the improved Pt/C performance in the GDE after CeO_x/C was added over the entire current range. The higher mass-specific activity observed for the Pt/C+ CeO_x/C compared to the CeO_x -free reference sample is in agreement with our RRDE data. However, in the latter case, the difference was less visible, which can be related to the differences in the methodology for the preparation of catalytic layers and test conditions. It should be remembered that the homogeneity of the catalytic layers can have a large impact on the assessment of the final catalytic performance. Due to the fast evaporation of the solvent at elevated temperature during spray-coating for GDE testing, we probably can get a more uniformly catalytic layer compared to drop-casting (with slow evaporation of solvent at room temperature for RRDE testing).

4. Conclusions

The three-component hybrid catalytic materials, which utilize low-Pt-content benchmark carbon-supported Pt nanoparticles modified with substoichiometric cerium oxides, have exhibited promising electrocatalytic properties toward ORR in acid medium. Among important issues are the existence of activating interactions between CeO_x and platinum nanostructures in addition to specific stabilizing interactions between CeO_x and carbon carriers. Consequently, the presence of the metal oxide additive affects the stability and selectivity of low Pt content electrocatalysts during ORR in acid medium. In this respect, application of the CeO_x/C additive, which is synthesized by microwave-assisted hydrothermal method, has most effectively promoted the 4-electron reduction of oxygen, i.e., it has led to the lowest amounts of the undesirable hydrogen peroxide intermediate and the highest transfer numbers during ORR. It is reasonable to expect that the observed positive enhancement effects reflect favorable electron transfers from substoichiometric CeO_x to Pt sites, as could be postulated on the basis of

Fig. 10. Galvanodynamic steady-state polarization responses for the oxygen reduction on gas diffusion electrodes. Oxygen flux: 50 mL min^{-1} ; temperature: 60°C ; electrolyte: oxygen saturated 0.5 mol dm^{-3} H_2SO_4 .

NAP-XPS data. In addition to carbon – CeO_x interactions, the spillover of electronic interactions between Pt and CeO_x (possibly also mediated by the carbon species present in the system) could also contribute to the overall stabilizing of the low-Pt content hybrid electrocatalysts.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

A. Kostuch: Conceptualization, Investigation, Data curation, Resources, Methodology, Formal analysis, Visualisation, Funding acquisition, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **E. Negro:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **G. Pagot:** Investigation, Data curation, Resources. **S. Zoladek:** Investigation, Data curation, Resources. **I. A. Rutkowska:** Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **O. Siamuk:** Investigation, Data curation. **A. Chmielnicka:** Investigation. **V. Di Noto:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **P. J. Kulesza:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. All authors have approved the final version of the manuscript.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.cattod.2024.114889](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2024.114889).

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